

Redefining Womanhood: A Thematic Analysis of Namitha Gokhale's Gods, Graves and Grandmother

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Abstract

After independence, Indian English Literature has seen advent of women writers who unleashed a variety of themes and explored different genres. During the last two decades, Indian English fiction has a remarkable achievement and Namitha Gokhale established herself as one of the greatest women writers of India. Her literary works are based on difference themes especially focusing on women's problems. "God, Graves and Grandmother", her second novel portrays women who transform themselves from weak individuals to strong individuals fighting against all the odds of life. It is the story of a girl Gudiya and her grandmother Ammi, who fall from the riches to rags, when they come to Delhi. But the novel depicts how Grandmother changes their lives by becoming a saint and Gudiya growing into independent woman after undergoing self-realization. This paper explores how the main characters use their inner ability and strength to step out of a man's control and reclaim the dignity. They empower themselves by slightly modifying the societal norms and regain the lost glory and wealth.

Keywords: Transform, independent, self-realization, inner ability, dignity, empower

INTRODUCTION:

Indian women writers have started focusing on the issues of female exploitation and gender inequalities existing in our society and they have showcased these themes in their literary works in a remarkable way. Women writers like Anitha Desai, Shashi Deshpande, Jhumpa

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Lahiri and others gave voice to their struggles by exploring the inner consciousness of the female characters. Namitha Gokhale also belongs to the same set of writers who successfully portrayed the gender issues and exploitation of women in her works. Namitha Gokhale was born in Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh in the year 1956. She studied English Literature at Delhi University. Her passion for literature started at an early age and at the age of 17, she began editing and managing a film magazine called Super. She started writing the novels after the magazine was closed in early 1980s. Her first novel 'Paro: Dreams of Passion' was published in 1984 and she has written fiction and nonfictional works also. She is a founder and co-director of Jaipur Literature Festival. She received Sahitya Akademi Award in 2021 for her novel "Things to leave behind". She has written more than twenty literary works and has received many awards and appreciation across the world for her contribution to the literary world.

"God, Graves and Grandmother" is her second novel released in 1994. It deals with Gudiya, her Grandmother and Phoolwati who face major crisis in the male dominated society.

It is a story of Gudiya and her grandmother, Ammi who struggle for survival in a new place Delhi, which is not only known for its grandeur but also the struggles and survivals. After reaching Delhi, Grandmother, who was a prostitute and enjoyed wealth in her big mansion, but her daughter deserts both of them as she elopes with a man. Grandmother tries to survive in an unknown place and protect her grand daughter from the exploitation and struggles. Grandmother is portrayed as very intelligent and strong woman, who has :

"Grandmother had abandoned her burka the day we arrived.....a virtuous woman's curses may follow you." (p. 12)

It depicts the lives of women who try to fight against societal norms and showcases the ability of women to create their own paths despite the difficulties. Ammi with her intellect and sharp mind successfully uses superstitions of people to build a life for her family. She evolves into a respectable spiritual guru from a marginalized person because of her intelligence and persistent efforts. She portrays emergence of liberated and bold women who demonstrate courage and will to live an independent life breaking the societal constraints.

In this novel, Namitha Gokhale shows how an elderly lady, Ammi, a former prostitute cleverly manipulates superstitions of people and secures a place for herself as a saintly person

in the hearts of the lower- and middle-class people. She gains their trust and influence and establishes a temple that gives her and Gudiya a source of income and stability in life.

Another character called Phoolwati is also portrayed as a very strong, loyal and caring person who lives independent life and takes care of Gudiya with a motherly love. After the death of her husband, she leads an independent life instead of grieving his death. She rebuilds her life after meeting Ammi and Gudiya. After Ammi's death, Phoolwati takes care of Gudiya as well as the temple.

In the beginning of the story, Gudiya is shown as an innocent girl devoid of worldly wisdom. From childhood, she dreams of becoming a film star, marry a famous person and travel by air. She changes her name as Pooja Abhimanyu Singh and selects a rich looking man's picture as her father. She always wanted to escape from her house because of her mother's profession as a prostitute and as she does not know who is her real father. But her grandmother Ammi always takes care of her and tries to provide good life and financial support. She sees a young handsome man playing a musical instrument in a grand procession and gets attracted to his charm and elegance. He calls himself as Kalki. But an elderly Pandit Kailash Sastry warns that this man will bring destruction. He tells about Hindu belief that when the world reaches its peak point of corruption and evil, Kalki will come on a white horse to revive the righteousness and save the world.

“Handsome and a king among men, he will be armed with a huge axe; a new age will bein, when, once again, virtue and happiness will reign on the earth” (p.134)

Pandit Kailash Sastry when approached by Phoolwati about Gudiya's marriage, he warns of a hidden trouble to Gudiya as the horoscopes are not matching. Later on, Gudiya comes to know that this young man does not have a family, an orphan like herself and just goes by the name Kalki. She realizes that he is greedy and self-interested. But she marries him as she become pregnant because of her physical relation with Kalki, later on she realizes her mistake and stars living Shiv Mohan's house to start a new life.

She starts seeing similarities between her destiny and her mother's but she decides not to become like her mother who deserted her for the sake a marital life with her lover. Gudiya maintains resilient and strong demeanor after her marriage. She sends Kalki to Bombay by

giving her jewelry and saved money but he never returns to take care of Gudiya and their child. At this point of her life, Phoolwati becomes her refuge and protector, who provides shelter to Gudiya.

After Kalki goes away, Gudiya longs for his physical presence but feels relieved as his absence frees her from his domination and control. She realizes it was her mistake to accept him into her life as she always wanted a father like figure or male to take care of her and also unconsciously lives her life according to the societal norms and expectations which caused a great damage to her life. Gudiya gives birth to a daughter named Mallika and lives under the support of Phoolwati. After he leaves to Bombay, Kalki never comes back or contacts her. While going through the wedding pictures, Gudiya realizes that the memories are now distant and surreal. With the time passing, she interprets those memories through the lens of nostalgia and fantasy. She realizes that her innocence as a young girl and teenage love towards Kalki made her the victim of distress and exploitation. But later on, Gudiya becomes strong and independent woman taking care of her child and her grandmother's temple with the help of Phoolwati. Lack of parental love and guidance, change of life style from wealth to poverty and teenage adrenal rush led Gudiya into troubled life but women like her grandmother and Phoolwati gave her safety and assurance to have independent thinking and self-reliance.

CONCLUSION:

Namitha Gokhale has successfully portrayed women's quest for liberation and identity which is experienced not only in India but all over the world. She sheds light on the problems, stereo typed thoughts of people, fears of women and challenges encountered by women due to societal stigmas. She also shows feminine qualities of woman through Gudiya; honesty and motherly love through Phoolwati; smartness and intelligence through the character of Grandmother, Ammi. Namitha Gokhale voices the agony of women, female exploitation and demands justice and freedom for marginalized women. Women should not be treated as just object of enjoyment and lust. She should be treated as equal to men and respected with dignity. Her women characters are the representation of such modern and liberated women, who successfully rebuild their lives and become independent women and get their identity.

Namitha Gokhale has proved many a times that she is one of the greatest Indian women writers who is getting laurels to the nations through her literary works.

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